

BY-COVID Spring 23 Use Cases Workshop: Integration of socioeconomic data in observational studies on vaccine effectiveness

Workshop report

Project Title (grant agreement No)	BY-COVID Grant Agreement 101046203
Project Acronym (EC Call)	BY-COVID
WP No & Title	WP5 - A continuously evolving demonstrator project feeding the changing research questions that surface during an on-going pandemic to solutions.
Authors	Vasso Kalaitzi, CESSDA/DANS-KNAW; Simon Saldner, CESSDA/DANS-KNAW; Nina Van Goethem (Sciensano);
Contributors	Enrique Bernal Delgado (IACS) Francisco Estupiñán-Romero (IACS) Jeroen Belien (ELIXIR-NL/VUmc & Health-RI) Robin Navest (Lygature) Iris Van Dam (Sciensano) Laura Van den Borre (Sciensano-VUB) Ricarda Braukmann (DANS-KNAW) Angelica Maineri (ODISSEI) Nora Bünemann (EUR, PDPC) Daniela Skugor (SHARE Belgium)
Acknowledgements	Cees Hof (DANS) Ellen Carbo (ZonMw)

	Ingrid Dillo (DANS) Lisa Cavillot (Sciensano) Louise Bezuidenhout (DANS / ISIDORE) Margreet Bloemers (ZonMw) Mirjam Knol (RIVM) Olivia Genten (Sciensano) Pierre Hubin (Sciensano) Shona Cosgrove (Sciensano)
Version	1.0
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.7985917

History

Version	Date	Changes	Contributors
0.1	25-05-2023	First draft	Vasso Kalaitzi, Nina van Goethem, Simon Saldner
0.2	14-07-2023	Contributions, suggestions	Enrique Bernal Delgado, Francisco Estupiñán-Romero, Jeroen Belien, Robin Navest, Iris Van Dam, Laura Van den Borre, Ricarda Braukmann, Angelica Maineri, Nora Bünemann, Daniela Skugor
1.0	10-08-2023	Revised version	Vasso Kalaitzi, Simon Saldner

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Funded by
the European Union

Abbreviations and Acronyms

CBS	Statistics Netherlands
CDC	CESSDA Data Catalogue
CDM	The Common Data Model
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FDP	FAIR Data Point
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
LOST	Legal, Organisational, Semantic and Technical
ODISSEI	Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations
PICO	Population Intervention Comparison Outcome
RCT	Randomised Controlled Trial
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SANE	Secure ANalytical Environment
SHARE	Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SSHOC-NL	Social Science and Humanities Open Cloud for the Netherlands
STATBEL	Statistics Belgium
WP	Work Package

Table of contents

Executive Summary	1
1. Introduction	2
2. Methodology	3
3. Main points from the presentations	3
3.1 BY-COVID Baseline Use Case - Enrique Bernal-Delgado, Senior Health Services and Policy Researcher, IACS	4
3.2. The DANS Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities: enabling FAIR data in the Dutch SSH community - Ricarda Braukmann, Data Station Manager Social Sciences, DANS-KNAW	5
3.3. The ODISSEI Portal: collecting metadata from Dutch data providers (Angelica Maineri, Erasmus University Rotterdam/ODISSEI)	6
3.4. Health-RI COVID19 project - Experiences and bottlenecks re: SSH data (Jeroen Belien, Amsterdam UMC & Health-RI)	7
3.5. Data landscape for infectious diseases surveillance in Belgium and use of socio-economic indicators - Nina Van Goethem & Lisa Cavillot, Sciensano	7
4. Breakout sessions - Contribution towards workshop objectives	9
4.1 Socioeconomic aspects that are relevant indicators/factors at individual and area levels; Cross-fertilisation	9
4.2 Data sources that are relevant for the SSH and could be integrated in the COVID-19 Data Portal	10
4.3 Dutch-Belgian landscape: aspects to take into account with regards to data accessing and data mobilisation; Data requirements at organisational/disciplinary level	12
4.4 Multidisciplinarity and reproducibility aspects for the Baseline Use Case	13
5. Conclusions	14

Executive Summary

This report presents the findings of the “BY-COVID Spring 23 Use Cases Workshop Integration of socioeconomic data in observational studies on vaccine effectiveness”. The workshop was organised in the context of the BY-COVID project work package 5 (WP5) “A continuously evolving demonstrator project feeding the changing research questions that surface during an on-going pandemic to solutions” with the support of WP6 “Engage, train and build capacity with national and international stakeholders”. The event took place in The Hague, the Netherlands at the premises of NWO, the Dutch Research Council on April 26th 2023 and was co-organised by CESSDA¹/DANS-KNAW,² Sciensano,³ and IACS.⁴

A particular focus was placed on the Netherlands and Belgium, featuring multiple key actors predominantly from the social sciences domain, both internal and external to the BY-COVID project. Bringing together a diverse group of stakeholders, the workshop aimed to achieve the following goals:

- To promote further development of the BY-COVID Baseline Use Case,⁵ and stimulate community discussion around it;
- To highlight relevant initiatives and practices in the Dutch and Belgian landscape;
- To discuss issues surrounding socioeconomic data requirements, mobilisation, and protection in different national contexts in the form of breakout sessions;
- To highlight how real-world vaccine effectiveness can be estimated in a causal framework by combining administrative, health and care data with data on socioeconomic factors.

The present report further describes the workshop, highlights the main points of discussion, and identifies outcomes and implications for the project moving forward. The report is a collaborative effort with contributions from workshop participants, and other community stakeholders. It also aspires to be of further use for the BY-COVID project and relevant initiatives.

¹ CESSDA ERIC: CESSDA stands for Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives and ERIC stands for European Research Infrastructure Consortium. www.cessda.eu/

² Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS): an institute of KNAW, the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences, and NWO, the Dutch Research Council. dans.knaw.nl/en/

³ Sciensano: Belgian institute for health. www.sciensano.be/

⁴ IACS: Aragonese Institute of Health Sciences. www.iacs.es/

⁵ Meurisse, Marjan, Van Goethem, Nina, Estupiñán-Romero, Francisco, González-Galindo, Javier, Royo-Sierra, Santiago, Martínez-Lizaga, Natalia, & Bernal-Delgado, Enrique. (2023). BY-COVID - WP5 - Baseline Use Case: SARS-CoV-2 vaccine effectiveness assessment - Study protocol (1.0.3). Zenodo. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7825979

1. Introduction

The BY-COVID project's ambition is to enable accessing, analysing, linking, and processing of data and tools across disciplines and borders in response to COVID-19 and other pandemics. As such, it aims to demonstrate the value of connecting people, infrastructures and data resources from different disciplines for pandemic preparedness. The work package 5 (WP5) - "A continuously evolving demonstrator project feeding the changing research questions that surface during an ongoing pandemic to solutions", provides the driving use cases feeding into the important and evolving research questions that surface during an ongoing pandemic with a goal to generate solutions.

Within WP5, the Baseline Use Case is prototyping a workflow that provides a structured process to leverage observational real-world data sources to respond to policy-relevant questions. During the first half of the project, this workflow has been developed to provide an answer to the first research question with regard to the real-world effectiveness of SARS-CoV-2 vaccination in populations spanning national borders.⁶ However, estimating a causal relationship by leveraging observational data sources often requires adjustment for potential confounding factors during the statistical analysis.

This implies the need for detailed individual-level data to meet for the information requirements that have been specified in a Common Data Model (CDM).⁷ As such, the Baseline Use Case entails the mobilisation and linkage of heterogeneous data sources from different domains (including social sciences, public health, molecular life sciences and medical sciences). Integrating data sources from different domains, including those originating from Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), requires a cross-disciplinary approach.

Moreover, as the Baseline Use Case aims to assess vaccine effectiveness across national borders, the different national contexts should be taken into account. Therefore, this workshop aimed to stimulate cross-disciplinary and cross-border exchanges on the integration of socio-economic data in observational studies on vaccine effectiveness to further promote and contribute to the development of the Baseline Use Case.

⁶ Meurisse, Marjan, Van Goethem, Nina, Estupiñán-Romero, Francisco, González-Galindo, Javier, Royo-Sierra, Santiago, Martínez-Lizaga, Natalia, & Bernal-Delgado, Enrique. (2023). BY-COVID - WP5 - Baseline Use Case: SARS-CoV-2 vaccine effectiveness assessment - Study protocol (1.0.3). Zenodo. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7551181

⁷ Estupiñán-Romero, Francisco, Van Goethem, Nina, Meurisse, Marjan, González-Galindo, Javier, & Bernal-Delgado, Enrique. (2023). BY-COVID - WP5 - Baseline Use Case: SARS-CoV-2 vaccine effectiveness assessment - Common Data Model Specification (1.1.0). Zenodo. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7572373

2. Methodology

The organising team followed an approach that aimed at organising an interactive workshop with diverse participation of a wide stakeholder spectrum, including key research institutions, data holders and policymakers mainly from Belgium and the Netherlands related to pandemic preparedness. In particular, the event focused on stakeholders with experience and expertise on Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) topics and associated data. The list of participants was carefully selected to include organisations both internal and external to the BY-COVID project and with a wide range of profiles and roles for pandemic preparedness: RIVM, Sciensano, Amsterdam UMC, DANS also on behalf of CESSDA, Erasmus University Rotterdam, Health-RI, IACS, Lygature, ODISSEI, SHARE Belgium, the University of Antwerp, and ZonMw.

The programme was balanced between first, an informative part of presentations complemented by a Q&A session, and second, a more interactive part of breakout sessions in three roundtables. The participants were asked to select the topics of their preference beforehand, to ensure that the contributions would be according to the participants' interests and expertise, and foster a comfortable environment and collaboration.

The present report has been compiled by the workshop organisers with the contribution of the workshop participants and selected members of the community who were unable to attend the event. It is openly available⁸ on the BY-COVID Zenodo community,⁹ and we welcome any additional feedback.

3. Main points from the presentations

The first part of the workshop was dedicated to a set of presentations¹⁰ to familiarise the group of participants with the BY-COVID project and its Baseline Use Case, as well as with other relevant initiatives, a number of them also related to the integration of social sciences data in the Dutch and Belgian landscape. Furthermore, these presentations had the goal to provide some context and inspiration for further discussion during the breakout sessions.

An introduction and warm welcome by Ingrid Dillo, Deputy Director at DANS, provided some information about the role of DANS as an organisation and as a member of CESSDA with regard to the SSH domain, while it also made a reference to the RDA COVID-19 Guidelines and Recommendations¹¹ as a significant resource.

⁸ The Workshop Report and supplementary materials are available at the following DOI: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7985916

⁹ zenodo.org/communities/bycovid

¹⁰ All presentation slides discussed in this section can be found as related identifiers to Workshop Report DOI above, as well as in footnotes under each of the subsections below.

¹¹ RDA COVID-19 Working Group. (2020). RDA COVID-19 Recommendations and Guidelines on Data Sharing (1.0). doi.org/10.15497/rda00052

3.1 BY-COVID Baseline Use Case - Enrique Bernal-Delgado, Senior Health Services and Policy Researcher, IACS¹²

The introduction was followed by a presentation by Enrique Bernal-Delgado, Senior health services and policy researcher, IACS who spoke about the BY-COVID Baseline Use Case. In his presentation, Bernal-Delgado spoke about the idea behind the BY-COVID project, which aims to prepare relevant stakeholders for the next pandemic, based on the experience of the COVID-19 crisis. He described how BY-COVID WP5 is prototyping a methodological workflow that would allow the development of research questions based on “PICO”,¹³ which involves standardising a workflow that is common to any policy-relevant research question, and is standard in population health research.

A research question on the real-life effectiveness of vaccines has been used to mobilise routine data,¹⁴ using population data that covers virtually the whole population residing in the participant countries, with a view to emulate a Randomised Controlled Trial (RCT). The routine data reused in this use case is sensitive data, which allows testing the application of measure to comply with GDPR and ethical principles, thus developing upon the data-mobilisation principle (federated approach), the limitation of purpose (data application based on the thorough research protocol) and the minimisation principle (stemming from a common data model that respond the minimal data requirements to address the causal question). Resorting to a federated approach requires heavy efforts in legal, organisational, semantic and technical (LOST) interoperability. The computational architecture of this BY-COVID federated approach¹⁵ is based on a coordination hub and several data hubs in different countries in Europe that are participating in the Use Case. The coordination hub prepares the code, the data hubs run the code, the local outputs (non-sensitive aggregated results) are sent back to the coordination hub, and the coordination hub compiles the results and performs a meta-analysis.

Thus, what is shared is not sensitive data (that remains under the jurisdiction of the local data holders) but aggregated results, anonymous in nature, and just subject to the disclosure policies of the institution (data hub) providing access to the health data. The workflow includes several digital objects, pieces that can be reused in other projects (the CDM, important also in terms of syntactic (structure and formatting requirements) and semantic interoperability; a synthetic dataset that allows the preparation of the analytical pipeline, before submitting the code to the participant nodes, and the analytical algorithms. All the code is implemented within a software container (a Docker image) that *de facto* acts

¹² The IACS presentation is available on Zenodo at DOI: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7993139

¹³ This format creates a "well-built" question that identifies four concepts: (1) the Population, (2) the Intervention, (3) the Comparison, and (4) the Outcome(s)

¹⁴ These are usually data collected on a continuous basis obtained for administrative and clinical purposes without specific a priori research goals, including electronic medical records, administrative data, and registries.

¹⁵ González-García, J., Estupiñán-Romero, F., Tellería-Orriols, C. et al. Coping with interoperability in the development of a federated research infrastructure: achievements, challenges and recommendations from the JA-InfAct. Arch Public Health 79, 221 (2021). doi.org/10.1186/s13690-021-00731-z

as a secure processing environment.¹⁶ In this particular use case, where there is a need to demonstrate a causal association, the analytical pipeline is more complex and requires the addition of matching algorithms (to allow compliance with the principle of conditional¹⁷ exchangeability) and imputation algorithms to adequately treat data missingness. At the end of the participant nodes, after running the code they obtain as local results, different interactive HTML reports.

Closing his presentation, Bernal-Delgado referred to the importance of including social science data in the Baseline Use Case (i.e. in the workflow). At the current stage, socioeconomic status is included in the model as an ecological variable. Ideally, to better understand the effect of socioeconomic status both on the uptake of the vaccination program and on the actual reduction of infection, there is a need for the inclusion of individual socioeconomic information.

3.2. The DANS Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities: enabling FAIR data in the Dutch SSH community - Ricarda Braukmann, Data Station Manager Social Sciences, DANS-KNAW¹⁸

Ricarda Braukmann, Data Station Manager Social Sciences at DANS-KNAW, presented the DANS Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities¹⁹ and its contribution towards enabling FAIR data in the Dutch SSH community. The DANS Data Station SSH, which was released at the beginning of June 2023, is a data archiving and publishing service for SSH data in the Netherlands and one of the four different domain-specific DANS Data Stations.

Braukmann presented examples of metadata fields that will be available in the Data Station, including SSH domain-specific fields, information on rights and reuse, and related materials. More focus was given on the SSH-specific metadata fields following the CESSDA guidelines and controlled vocabularies coming from CESSDA and the SSH community. Examples of SSH-specific metadata available through the Data Station include fields related to survey methodology such as sampling procedure, response rates, and weighting, as well as keyword fields linked to controlled vocabularies, in particular the European Language Social Science Thesaurus (ELSST),²⁰ and CESSDA topic classification.²¹

The Data Station is in principle open to any researcher who wants to archive and publish data, and the ratio between open access and restricted access to datasets is about half, due to the prevalence of sensitive and personal data in the SSH domain. The Data Station contains, among others, survey data, public use files from statistical data, oral history data,

¹⁶ A Docker image is a virtual environment solution to containerise all software tools required to run the analysis reproducibly by dealing with all potential dependencies between the different tools while isolating the stack from the system.

¹⁷ Conditional on observed confounders as identified in the causal model.

¹⁸ The DANS-KNAW presentation is available on Zenodo at DOI: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7867779

¹⁹ dans.knaw.nl/en/data-stations/social-sciences-and-humanities/

²⁰ elsst.cessda.eu/

²¹ vocabularies.cessda.eu/vocabulary/TopicClassification

interview data, and 200+ datasets on COVID-19. It is also connected to the ODISSEI portal,²² and the CESSDA Data Catalogue (CDC).²³

The DANS Data Station SSH provides a useful example of how SSH data can be archived and published following domain-specific requirements, and how this data can be connected and integrated with other platforms to become findable for reuse. Data from the Data Station is currently made available on the BY-COVID project's Covid-19 Data Platform through the CDC, the metadata of which is harvested by the platform.

3.3. The ODISSEI Portal: collecting metadata from Dutch data providers (Angelica Maineri, Erasmus University Rotterdam/ODISSEI)²⁴

Angelica Maineri, Data Manager at Erasmus University Rotterdam/ODISSEI (Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations) presented the ODISSEI Portal²⁵ which collects metadata from Dutch data providers, contributing to the goal of building a federated infrastructure for social & economic sciences.

The SSH data landscape is scattered across numerous repositories and data providers at different institutions, while official, individual-level statistical data from the governmental agency Statistics Netherlands (CBS), consists of pseudonymised microdata that can only be accessed under strict conditions. The ODISSEI Portal aims to provide a layer between these different stakeholders. The data providers only share detailed metadata and remain in full control of the actual data; the metadata exchange process has been useful for some providers to improve their own metadata management systems. ODISSEI is also working on connecting the Portal to their Secure ANalytical Environment (SANE) platform for sensitive data, as well as computing facilities hosted by SURF, the national academic computing/infrastructure provider, and CBS.

The ODISSEI Portal runs on Dataverse, with searchable metadata from the CBS microdata catalogue, LISS panel, and SSH collections from DANS and DataverseNL. Moving forward, ODISSEI aims to enhance searchability through controlled vocabularies and multilingual support, as well as adding metadata from more providers, including partners involved in SSHOC-NL,²⁶ and the CESSDA Data Catalogue through which metadata will be added to the BY-COVID COVID-19 Data Portal.

²² odissei-data.nl/en/

²³ datacatalogue.cessda.eu/

²⁴ The ODISSEI presentation is available on Zenodo at: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7970499

²⁵ portal.odissei.nl/

²⁶ An initiative called Social Science and Humanities Open Cloud for the Netherlands (SSHOC-NL) has recently been awarded funding by the Dutch funder NWO:
odissei-data.nl/en/2023/02/nwo-roadmap-grant-for-digital-infrastructure-social-sciences-and-humanities/

3.4. Health-RI COVID19 project - Experiences and bottlenecks re: SSH data (Jeroen Belien, Amsterdam UMC & Health-RI)²⁷

Jeroen Belien from Amsterdam UMC & Health-RI presented the Health-RI COVID-19 Data Portal²⁸ and their experiences and bottlenecks regarding SSH data. Health-RI is a public-private partnership that aims to promote the reuse of health data through an integrated health data infrastructure, and the COVID-19 Data Portal helps users find and reuse COVID-19 related observational data from Dutch health care providers.

The infrastructure has been created on the principles of machine actionable data and FAIR, as well as metadata standards and vocabulary services, while community input has been crucial. Building the infrastructure was based on, and with, the local infrastructures used in hospitals and research institutes, e.g. CASTOR.²⁹ Data governance represents one of the main challenges, while data policies were often not in place and had to be considered/established. Belien presented to the participants the project's data governance workflow and results, noting that the data can be opened for reuse. In order to comply with data governance and regulatory aspects, a data governance workflow was developed that allows users to request data via the portal, that can be duly reviewed by data holders and other parties, before the data is provided to the requestor. In addition, a secure processing environment, myDRE,³⁰ is used to enhance the safety of secondary data use (for ETL (extract, transform, load) processes towards the agreed upon WHO/ISARIC data dictionary by data provider as well data processing and analysis by data requestor). Furthermore, in this infrastructure secure analytical as well as computing facilities are embedded.

Technologies like the FAIR Data Point (FDP) were set up to enhance the findability of results, and have been implemented by/with most data providers. Belien concluded that their experience shows that, although linking data from different domains is possible, interpreting laws and regulations, as well as linking data at the subject level are the main obstacles.

3.5. Data landscape for infectious diseases surveillance in Belgium and use of socio-economic indicators - Nina Van Goethem & Lisa Cavillot, Sciensano³¹

The first part of the workshop concluded with a presentation from Nina Van Goethem & Lisa Cavillot from Sciensano, who talked about the data landscape for infectious diseases surveillance in Belgium and the use of socio-economic indicators.

Van Goethem presented a schematic overview showing that there exist many different systems and related activities for the surveillance of infectious diseases, determinants and interventions. The data sources are heterogeneous and include specific disease registries,

²⁷ The Health-RI presentation is available on Zenodo at: zenodo.org/record/7982090

²⁸ www.health-ri.nl/covid-19-data-portal

²⁹ www.castoredc.com/

³⁰ mydre.org/

³¹ The presentation by Sciensano is available on Zenodo at: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7988732

laboratory data, primary care data, hospital data, and reimbursement data. Some of these activities are not formally described as public health surveillance systems, but do provide essential ongoing information. For example, Statistics Belgium (STATBEL) provides information on the size of the potentially exposed population and demographic characteristics of the Belgian population. Also, administrative data sources such as absenteeism and reimbursement data can be used to measure the societal impact of certain infectious diseases. The appearance of COVID-19 has transformed the infectious disease surveillance landscape in Belgium. There was a high need to adapt existing systems and also to establish new surveillance systems at different levels. This led to an ever-growing amount of data. Based on the data that is being generated, Sciensano aims to provide answers to policy relevant questions, such as the clinical impact of SARS-CoV-2 variants which may have implications to safeguard the healthcare capacity, and questions related to vaccine effectiveness to evaluate vaccination programs.

The relevance of the data for policy-making of course depends on the timeliness of the results. A long-lasting public health crisis like COVID-19 also demonstrates how the questions change over time. Therefore, data infrastructures should be flexible. Based on the new questions that are being raised, the need to establish or connect additional data sources might occur. It is a two-way interaction between the data that is generated and the policy-relevant questions that need answers. To work in a more structured way that is hypothesis-driven instead of data-driven, Sciensano established a causal framework³² to study the research question which consists of different consecutive steps (comparable to the BY-COVID Baseline Use Case). A crucial step in this process was to translate the causal model into data requirements and build a data model. In Belgium, the data infrastructure meeting these requirements has been established in the context of the LINK-VACC project,³³ linking vaccine administration data, data from COVID-19 tests, socioeconomic data, hospital data, etc.

Next, Cavillot outlined the use of socio-economic indicators in the research of Sciensano. STATBEL data were used to study the sociodemographic and socioeconomic disparities in the uptake of COVID-19 vaccinations. The focus was placed on sociodemographic and socioeconomic exposure. The sociodemographic indicators used were the migration background and the household type, while the socioeconomic indicators used were the income, education and employment status. Cavillot also referred to the HELICON project³⁴ and the valuation of administrative data sources through linkages at individual level.

³² Van Goethem, N., Serrien, B., Vandromme, M. et al. Conceptual causal framework to assess the effect of SARS-CoV-2 variants on COVID-19 disease severity among hospitalized patients. Arch Public Health 79, 185 (2021). doi.org/10.1186/s13690-021-00709-x

³³ LINK-VACC project: www.sciensano.be/en/projects/linking-registers-covid-19-vaccine-surveillance

³⁴ HELICON project: www.brain-helicon.be/

4. Breakout sessions - Contribution towards workshop objectives

The second half of the workshop was devoted to breakout sessions and discussions of relevant topics. Three separate breakout session tables were organised that each discussed three of the following four topics:

1. Socioeconomic aspects that are relevant indicators/factors at individual and area levels; Cross-fertilisation
2. Data sources that are relevant for the SSH and could be integrated in the COVID-19 Data Portal
3. Dutch-Belgian landscape: aspects to consider regarding data accessing and data mobilisation; Data requirements at organisational/disciplinary level
4. Multidisciplinarity and reproducibility aspects for the Baseline Use Case

Following the breakout sessions, a rapporteur for each group summarised the discussions and conclusions regarding each of the three topics they discussed. Following this, the floor was opened up for everyone to raise questions and remarks. The following four sections aim to summarise the points discussed for each of the four topics, both within the breakout sessions and during the subsequent discussions.

4.1 Socioeconomic aspects that are relevant indicators/factors at individual and area levels; Cross-fertilisation

The participants involved in the session indicated that socioeconomic indicators are interesting both at individual and aggregated levels (i.e. at area level) in relevant research. The individual level indicators are needed to discover intersectionality of risks and cumulative disadvantages.³⁵ For the area level indicators, challenges arise in deciding how to aggregate data and choose variables (e.g. aggregating individual level data vs. using publicly available aggregated data). Furthermore, the availability of data also depends on the research question and/or the purpose of use, that can lead to a wide spectrum of socioeconomic factors and relevant data sources to be considered (e.g. administrative data as well as surveys). In most cases, it is preferred to start from the hypothesis and not from the data availability. Emphasis should be placed on the research question and the storytelling of the data.

The participants of this session drew from their own experiences to reflect on specific socioeconomic factors that are relevant to vaccine effectiveness, response to future

³⁵ Intersectionality is a theoretical framework aimed at understanding how different systems of oppression interact and create unique effects. Because different types of inequality can be mutually reinforcing, it is recommended to analyse and address them simultaneously; Cumulative disadvantage (CD) refers to the accumulating influence of social, behavioural, and biological processes and their interplay on health over the life course.

pandemics and data-driven policymaking. In the case of SHARE³⁶ Belgium, indicators related to age and the labour market have rendered significant information on the effects of COVID-19 with regard to how the pandemic affected employment, family and the financial and social status of people over 50 years of age. During the pandemic, SHARE temporarily switched from face-to-face interviewing (CAPI) to telephone interviews (CATI). A special SHARE-Corona questionnaire was developed that asked respondents (50 years and older) about their circumstances before and after the COVID-19 outbreak. Various life domains were covered; i.e., health and health behaviour, mental health, infections and healthcare, changes in work and economic situation, and social networks.³⁷

At the same time, the Pandemic & Disaster Preparedness Center (PDPC)³⁸ in the Netherlands worked with data on different population groups to identify the barriers and drivers towards uptake, acceptance and adherence to COVID-19 public health and social measures among underserved groups in the Netherlands.³⁹

One significant challenge that was identified in terms of linking data is connected to the fact that different organisations are involved as key stakeholders in a complex landscape. As the type of relevant organisations differs (e.g. RPOs, service providers, archives, individual researchers), these stakeholders can assume different roles or may experience difficulties deviating from these roles, as well as from a variety of vocabularies, needs and requirements. Further challenges are related to the various ways of operating in terms of procedures and data access policies and practices, anonymisation/pseudonymisation, as well as the potential lack of guidelines and transparency. To address these challenges, data stewards could potentially bridge this gap.

4.2 Data sources that are relevant for the SSH and could be integrated in the COVID-19 Data Portal

This session focused on identifying data sources that include socioeconomic data, which could be explored as potential sources to be integrated in the COVID-19 Data Portal as well as for other data platforms such as SHARE Belgium,⁴⁰ the ODISSEI Portal,⁴¹ the PDPC⁴² and Sciensano.⁴³

The discussion groups agreed on a number of parameters that affect the identification and suitability of potential data sources. Firstly, the data source must be able to provide the variables required to address the research question(s) at hand. Definitions and operationalisations of variables such as trust, socioeconomic level, or income bracket vary,

³⁶ SHARE: Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe, share-eric.eu/

³⁷ For more information about the data, visit share-eric.eu/data/.

³⁸ convergence.nl/pandemic-disaster-preparedness/

³⁹ convergence.nl/learning-from-a-crisis

⁴⁰ www.share-project.be/

⁴¹ odissei-data.nl/en/odissei-portal/

⁴² www.eur.nl/en/news/pandemic-disaster-preparedness-center-officially-opened

⁴³ www.sciensano.be/en

and may not always align with the aims or data model (e.g. the Baseline Use Case CDM) of the research project at hand. The adherence to certain technical specifications or standards such as the metadata schema used, registration with FAIRsharing, licence/access conditions, or data quality issues such as sample size and quality, are other important considerations. Finally, it is often important that data from different sources can be linked with each other, as in the Baseline Use Case. Preferably, this is done through a trusted party (e.g. the CBS in the Netherlands), but if this is not possible, another option is to indirectly link data via variables such as date of birth or postal code. However, such data and linkages are often sensitive in nature, and may require a data sharing agreement. The groups also highlighted the need for infrastructure development and guidelines in the area of data linkage.

The groups also discussed what additional types of data sources should be considered for the BY-COVID project. Administrative data, typically from official governmental sources, was highlighted as particularly important here. Such sources are often required to acquire data on e.g. infection and vaccination rates (including among certain groups and geographical areas), and demographics. Linking administrative data with research data can therefore provide crucial contextual information, but such linkages are challenging for the reasons already mentioned above. SHARE NL⁴⁴ was highlighted as a successful example of how to link administrative data with research data. In this case, administrative data from the Dutch CBS to the survey data collected by SHARE NL, and an equivalent approach will soon be implemented by SHARE Belgium. The group also highlighted how access conditions to administrative data sources, as well as what kind of data these sources can provide, may vary significantly between countries. In e.g. Scandinavian countries, governmental data sources tend to be linked or centralized, while in e.g. Belgium, the landscape is more fragmented. In the Netherlands, members of the PDPC reported that administrative data is often not linked, and that these sources also often lack socioeconomic data, highlighting the challenges of working with these data sources.

Finally, the BY-COVID Infectious Diseases Toolkit (IDTK)⁴⁵ was highlighted as a useful source of additional resources and materials. The IDTK aims to offer guidelines and examples on managing, analysing and visualising infectious diseases data. It has been designed to accommodate information from different domains, to showcase different solutions, and to expose national resources. It is being developed as part of the BY-COVID project.

⁴⁴ www.share-project.nl

⁴⁵ www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org

4.3 Dutch-Belgian landscape: aspects to take into account with regards to data accessing and data mobilisation; Data requirements at organisational/disciplinary level

Special emphasis was placed on the Dutch-Belgian landscape in this event, in order to uncover similarities, differences and facilitate knowledge exchange that will be useful for pandemic preparedness.

Both countries seemed to have faced similar challenges in terms of data accessing, which was confirmed by the main research institutes for public health in the two countries that were present, namely RIVM and Sciensano. Both countries observed some regional fragmentation that derives from different authorities at different levels, with the fragmentation being more obvious in Belgium, also due to language differences.

In terms of pandemic preparedness, several lessons learned could lead to more effective pandemic preparedness, however the data mobilisation remains low. In Belgium, the LINK-VACC project⁴⁶ has been set up to assess post-authorization surveillance of the COVID-19 vaccines and enables linkages of the vaccine registry that collects information on all administered COVID-19 vaccines, with other already existing databases that contain relevant and detailed information. The value of synthetic data⁴⁷ that resemble real data is amplified, as they are more accessible, thus facilitating preparation of statistical analysis scripts. This triggered further discussion on the need for both countries to prepare researchers to make newly generated data ready to use for future pandemic research, potentially even at the funding stage, and together with a high-level policy approach. It was also pointed out that countries with an existing good quality of online survey panels benefited. Harmonisation at the level of data, metadata and informed consent has also been noted as of high importance. Projects and initiatives like BY-COVID and PHIRI⁴⁸ could support this process. The contributions also pointed to certain risks related to relying too heavily on synthetic data sources in this context: The current methodology to create synthetic data is not suited to investigate small population groups or events with small numbers, and does not allow for longitudinal follow-up; the current (AI-based) methods learn from selection mechanisms already inherent to the original data and further distort the application and interpretation of results; and researchers will not be able to check the original data sources and flag problems, which leads to data quality at risk and reduced capacity building.

With regard to policymaking, several participant organisations have had the opportunity to contribute to COVID-19 pandemic policies, either in a direct or indirect way, through relevant task forces, by making their research available to the relevant ministries, acting as research funders, and/or by providing critical research infrastructure and expertise.

⁴⁶ www.sciensano.be/en/projects/linking-registers-covid-19-vaccine-surveillance

⁴⁷ Synthetic data is artificial data that is generated to reproduce the characteristics and structure of the original data.

⁴⁸ Population Health Information Research Infrastructure, www.phiri.eu

4.4 Multidisciplinarity and reproducibility aspects for the Baseline Use Case

Multidisciplinarity is an important topic of discussion, considering that the use of socioeconomic factors and data in health research tends to be rather limited. Even when socioeconomic factors are used, this tends to be limited to a rather limited and fundamental set of factors such as age, income, or education, rather than more complex indicators such as trust, socioeconomic level, or political attitudes. Integrating socioeconomic data can be challenging due to how such data is often sensitive, context-specific (e.g. different countries having different educational systems and definitions of education level), and lacking international standards, ontologies and vocabularies to avoid different interpretations. For these reasons, data sources (including Data Hubs included in the Use Case), often lack socioeconomic data, particularly at the individual level.

As mentioned in the above sections, linking and thereby enriching e.g. health data with sources of socioeconomic data also tends to be highly challenging, and one group highlighted how the BY-COVID Use Cases and Dutch Personal Health Train⁴⁹ by Health-RI have faced similar challenges in this regard. In general, linked and harmonised data, including on socioeconomic factors, can often be available at the EU level through sources such as EUROSTAT. However, such data tends to be general and aggregated, while more specific and individual-level data are often only available on the national/local level.

However, there are several tools, platforms and initiatives to facilitate cross-disciplinary cooperation. Some examples that were mentioned during this breakout session were the Dutch Personal Health Train⁵⁰ project, EUROSTAT, EUROBAROMETER, the Bioportal, the FIP Wizard,⁵¹ the FAIR-IMPACT project,⁵² the PDPC,⁵³ the Dutch COVID19 Data Portal,⁵⁴ Castor EDC,⁵⁵ as well as those presented during the workshop and summarised in previous sections of this report. In particular, CEDAR⁵⁶ was highlighted as a useful tool to contribute towards both multidisciplinarity and reproducibility. The tool facilitates cooperation between disciplines by producing better metadata, including the creation of machine-actionable metadata with controlled vocabularies, as well as by being open to every research discipline. Other tools that can aid with FAIRification, such as FIP Wizard⁵⁷ or GO FAIR,⁵⁸ can also contribute to multidisciplinarity and reproducibility in similar ways.

⁴⁹ www.health-ri.nl/initiatives/personal-health-train

⁵⁰ www.health-ri.nl/initiatives/personal-health-train

⁵¹ fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/

⁵² fair-impact.eu/

⁵³ convergence.nl/pandemic-disaster-preparedness/

⁵⁴ www.health-ri.nl/covid-19-data-portal

⁵⁵ www.castoredc.com/

⁵⁶ metadatacenter.org/

⁵⁷ ds-wizard.org

⁵⁸ www.go-fair.org/how-to-go-fair/

Finally, one of the groups emphasised a multidisciplinary aspect that they argue had not been covered in BY-COVID thus far, namely data on (potentially) zoonotic diseases. Given that many infectious diseases are zoonotic (potentially including COVID-19), the group argued that e.g. veterinary data on potentially zoonotic diseases may be important to prevent and tackle future outbreaks.

5. Conclusions

The BY-COVID Spring 23 Use Case Workshop: *Integration of socioeconomic data in observational studies on vaccine effectiveness*, gathered key data holders, data infrastructure experts, and researchers from the Netherlands and Belgium to collaborate on how socioeconomic data can be mobilised to contribute to research and prevention of infectious diseases such as COVID-19. The workshop directly feeds into the BY-COVID project's Baseline Use Case on vaccine effectiveness, which aims to demonstrate the value of linking data from multiple heterogeneous sources and disciplines through a federated infrastructure. The workshop also contributed to bringing together related initiatives from the Dutch and Belgian landscape, to share best practices and experiences on the use and sharing of data on infectious diseases and related data among researchers and practitioners.

The presentations in the first half of the workshop showcased recent progress in BY-COVID, together with adjacent developments in the wider Dutch and Belgian landscape. It is evident from these presentations that there is already significant capacity and expertise on data infrastructure related to infectious diseases and SSH in this landscape, and that this field is under rapid development. That said, the presentations also highlighted the challenges and limitations involved in this work, notably including data governance and security issues surrounding sensitive data. These presentations thus show the benefits that collaboration in this field can have in terms of cross-fertilisation, and the tackling of shared challenges.

The breakout sessions and round-table discussions in the second half of the workshop provided an opportunity to address the topics discussed in the first half, as well as four topics identified by the organisers related to: relevant SSH aspects and cross-fertilisation; data sources; the Dutch-Belgian landscape; and the issues surrounding multidisciplinary and reproducibility. The participants discussed how a multitude of SSH factors, both at an individual and aggregated level, are necessary to capture the cumulative disadvantages that can affect the spread of infectious diseases. Achieving this requires overcoming challenges surrounding how to link sensitive SSH data to other data, how to aggregate SSH data, as well as how to mobilise data from a complex landscape of stakeholders. The participants, however, identified a number of data sources that can potentially be mobilised, provided the right data requirements and technical specifications are met. In the Dutch-Belgian landscape, the participants concluded that, although there is significant

capacity and infrastructure in these countries, there is a fragmentation of domestic actors and a lack of connection to (inter)national partners, which points to a need for further coordination, harmonisation, and infrastructure development among these stakeholders.

This workshop gathered key Dutch and Belgian stakeholders involved with SSH and infectious diseases related data, both internal and external to the BY-COVID project. The workshop thus successfully contributed to further collaboration in this landscape, identified best practices, experiences and challenges surrounding the mobilisation and use of SSH data for infectious disease research and practice, and laid the ground for further developments both within the BY-COVID Baseline Use Case, as well as in the wider landscape. For future updates on BY-COVID Use Cases and other project-related developments, please visit the BY-COVID Website,⁵⁹ Zenodo Community,⁶⁰ as well as the COVID-19 Data Portal.⁶¹

⁵⁹ by-covid.org/

⁶⁰ zenodo.org/communities/bycovid/?page=1&size=20

⁶¹ www.covid19dataportal.org/

